

A Swiss sense of compromise: Planning a new museum building in an eco-friendly city

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The Natural History Museum of Geneva is a 200 years institution that has experienced, like many museums, several phases of expansion and relocation. Its current building, located in the left bank of the Geneva Lake, has recently celebrated its 50 years and is now facing several issues like modernizing the conservation of the fluid collections and expanding collection space, both in terms of safety regulations and of preventive care. During the initial planning procedures, we were able to convince the decision-makers to orientate the new project towards the building of an extension of the current structure rather than moving the collections to an off-site storage facility. On the other hand, this choice raised challenges regarding the preservation of the park surrounding the Museum and the feasibility of using the underground in a densely urbanized neighbourhood. The City of Geneva has developed ambitious priorities towards the ecological and social transition facing climate emergency: the Museum's project has also to comply with these criteria, in limiting the impact of the new structure in terms of energy and environment. The solution proposed has fulfilled all problematics in what can be seen as a compromise between the creation of new spaces for collection storage and research and the preservation of the Museum's urban and natural surroundings.

